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ABSTRACT

This review discusses the latest innovations, teaching technologies and techniques, and the most convenient and effective methods and techniques implemented in our education system. With the help of the technologies and methods listed below, students will have the opportunity to think quickly, creatively, and analyze the topic. At the same time, it will be possible to develop their worldview to a sufficient extent. This review shows effective methods in teaching.

Keywords: technology, method, innovation, cognitive, interactive, creative, simulation

INTRODUCTION

Concepts such as innovation in pedagogy, innovation activity, innovation pedagogy, and management of innovation processes in education emerged in the 1960s, when the concept of "educational technology" was recognized in the USA and Western European countries. At that time, centers and institutes of pedagogical innovations were organized in Europe. An analysis of sources providing information on the emergence of these concepts and the creation of an innovative educational theory shows that these concepts are aimed at reforming the education system through the technologization of the education system, introducing pedagogical technologies into the education system, increasing the effectiveness of education, ensuring the socialization of the individual, and in order to achieve certain successes in this regard, friendly relations with the child are established in the educational process. emerged as a result of an attempt to introduce a new scientific direction in the second half of the 80s of the last century, which was formed as a result of scientific research, according to which pedagogical activity is a combination of a creative process and pedagogical innovations.

MAIN PART

This made it possible to analyze the process of introduction and development of the teacher's innovative pedagogical activity. Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and the activities of teachers and students, and their implementation mainly uses interactive methods. Interactive methods are called collective thinking, that is, methods of pedagogical influence, and are considered an integral part of the content of education. The peculiarity of these methods is that they are implemented only through the joint activity of the teacher and students. Such a pedagogical cooperation process has its own characteristics, which include the following:

- forcing the student to be independent, think independently, create and search during the lesson;
- ensuring that students maintain a constant interest in knowledge during the learning process;
- to strengthen the student's interest in knowledge in an independent manner with a creative approach to each issue;
- the organization of the teacher's and student's constant collaborative activities requires training and professional development.

When assessing the effectiveness of innovative pedagogical technologies, factors such as their relevance to educational goals, integration into the learning process, active participation of students, and achievements in learning are analyzed. For example, the use of interactive games, simulations, and project methods can help students consolidate their knowledge, develop problem-solving skills, and teach teamwork. However, the effectiveness of these technologies depends on the pedagogical skills of the teacher, the quality of the learning materials, and the availability of technical tools. Pedagogical and psychological analysis shows that innovative pedagogical technologies are not just the use of technical means, but a strategy for radically changing the educational process and adapting it to the individual needs of students. This requires teachers to master new pedagogical approaches, develop new competencies in planning and managing the educational process. For this reason, along with the introduction of innovative technologies, it is necessary to improve the qualifications of teachers and improve the system of their support. Innovative pedagogical technologies are an important component of modern education and are aimed at improving the educational process. Their pedagogical and psychological analysis is aimed at optimizing educational content and methods, taking into account the individual characteristics, cognitive styles, and motivation of students.

CONCLUSION

Within the framework of this analysis, the effectiveness of the use of educational technologies, the active involvement of students in the learning process, the development of independent thinking and problem-solving skills are studied. In conclusion, it can be said that innovative educational technologies are one of the most effective technologies used in teaching biology. Innovative pedagogical technologies are an important component of modern education, helping students acquire deep and solid knowledge, develop independent thinking and problem-solving skills, and successfully adapt to life. Interactive games, project methods, collaborative learning and other innovative approaches make the learning process more interesting and effective, encouraging students to actively participate.

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